

Status Report

IUC17: Ontologies for defects in crystals

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The microstructure of materials is characterized by crystallographic defects, which ultimately determine the material properties. A representation of such defects and structures is at the heart of many studies or investigations conducted in NFDI-MatWerk. The aim of this infrastructure use case (IUC) is to develop semantic representations describing crystalline structures and crystalline defects (such as point defects, line defects, area and volume defects) and their temporal evolution and to test if these descriptions are well designed and applicable for different types of simulations, experiments and microscopy. Another aspect covered is aiding domain scientists in implementing ontologies in their everyday research. The combination of controlled vocabularies and software tools for generating linked open data ensures interoperability, while also offering the potential for data to be findable and reusable.

The integration of the terminology developed within this IUC is geared toward the activities of the participant projects:

- PP01 From atoms to turbine blades (CRC/TRR 103)
- PP11 Ontology Design for Dislocations (ERC MuDiLingo)
- PP18 Bundesanstalt für Materialforschung und -prüfung (BAM)
- PP21 FAIR Grain Boundaries in Simulations and Experiments (FAIR-GB)

Within the research activities of the mentioned participant projects, IUC17 focuses on the following application use cases and research data:

- **Application in atomistic simulations:**
Computational materials science uses methods and tools to predict and analyze the defect structure. Within this IUC, ontologies are developed that describe concepts of atomic structures as well as domain- and application level aspects of atomistic simulations. These ontologies allow interoperability on a technical and semantic level. Software tools that use these ontologies to automatically annotate atomic structures and simulation methods are developed. This ensures that the simulations performed with different workflow environments and software are interoperable and reusable. The developed software tool is open-source and available through software registries such as conda-forge and pypi.
- **Stacking fault energy calculation workflows:**
This application use case, that concentrates on the determination of stacking fault energy via the ANNNI Model entails: (i) generation of various structural configurations, and (ii) computation of energies associated with these configurations across a range of temperatures. The aim is to leverage the ontologies describing computational structures and atomistic simulations and use the integrated components on the relevant workflows.
- **FAIR Grain Boundaries:**
The objectives of the participant project are the development of consistent and extendable representations of the structure/properties of grain boundaries to foster the integration of data from high-resolution characterization experiments, atomistic simulations and machine learning. Within this IUC, the semantic aspects of planar defects description in different applications can be harmonized.
- **Hydrogen-microstructure interaction:**
The ontologies developed within IUC17 can be used beyond this use case, as the description of crystallographic defects is ubiquitous in material science. Particularly important are topics where certain phenomena are studied at the atomic level. PP20 and the DGM Expert Committee Hydrogen look into: (i) development of database and research data management for hydrogen effects in materials, specifically with Thermal Desorption Mass Spectrometry (TDMS) data which gives access to hydrogen trapping at defects; and, (ii) Mat-o-Lab use case on LLM for hydrogen: interplay of atomistic simulations, experimental data and theories on hydrogen embrittlement.

These use cases provide exemplary scenarios for domain scientists to leverage the advantages of harmonized semantics in their everyday research, taking a step towards FAIR data.

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